

Academic Analysis on Students' Ability to Use Completely Different Aspects of Orientation Points and Learning Situation

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Abstract

The study of the biological, social, and environmental forces that influence the way individuals think, behave, and learn is what is called psychology. This last point has been the focus of discussions in the field of special education aimed at helping teachers close the achievement gaps

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that exist among student groups. To find the answer to this question, we will need to explore educational psychology, which is the application of psychological principles to the field of special education. Some of the most important developments in special education, such as the reintegration of students with disabilities into general education classrooms, have been made possible as a direct result of studies in educational psychology. Educational psychologists can guide teaching procedures and help achieve better academic outcomes for students regardless of their skills, resources, or environment. This is because educational psychologists understand how individuals receive and remember information. This is extremely important for students with disabilities as they face a wide range of developmental disabilities of varying degrees. Aristotle and Plato are considered the founders of educational psychology; however, psychologists like Jean Piaget are credited with laying the groundwork for one of the most fundamental principles of educational psychology, which states that knowledge cannot be transferred from one person to another. Teachers can provide material in an interesting and appropriate way, but it is the student's responsibility to learn and remember the information presented. Constructivist learning theory, which states that students can only learn by building on existing knowledge, is based on the premise that this is the only way for students to acquire new knowledge. Another important tenet of constructivist theory is the concept of cooperative learning, which expresses the idea that if students are allowed to work with these challenges in groups, students will have an easier time solving the challenges and understanding the material. This is the case even though cognitive learning theory is one of the theories that shape how lessons are taught.

Keywords: *Student Orientation, Student and Learning, Student Learning and Different Aspects, Using Different Aspects in Learning*

1. Introduction

As a result of this dynamic movement, general education educators are increasingly responsible for educating students with and without disabilities, a task that comes with its own unique set of disabilities. The expertise of special educators, who can use their understanding of educational

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psychology in the classroom and contribute to creating an optimal environment for learning, is often used by general educators who need help.

2. The Impact of Educational Psychology on Schools and Students

The field of special education has been deeply reshaped because of educational psychology. Educators are now aware that most students with disabilities can achieve the same academic standards as their non-disabled peers; this is a significant development from the past when students with disabilities were isolated from the rest of the student population. However, for students with disabilities to be successful academically, their individual needs must be considered and met in a timely manner.

3. Adapting Instruction to Individual Students' Abilities and Challenges

When it comes to the education of children with disabilities, there is no cookie-cutter approach that can be used. Teachers diversify their lessons according to the recommendations of educational psychologists to ensure that every student, regardless of intellectual capacity, can gain experience. In addition to being adaptable, constantly evaluating students and working together, differentiated instruction emphasizes challenging work environments and group projects. These are student-centered concepts shared by the constructivist learning perspective. In the mainstreaming class, students with disabilities receive education together with their peers without disabilities. These students receive individual, small group, and whole-class education and can discuss the topics covered in the classroom with classmates of different abilities and interests. Creating a learning environment that is both stimulating and demanding is often more difficult.

What role does psychology play in education for students with exceptional needs? Educational psychology provides educators with the tools they need to train people with disabilities, some of whom otherwise do not have access to the high-quality education they deserve. This course focuses on the study of theories of behavior, learning and teaching, and human ontological development.

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Educational psychology principles will serve you well in the classroom as one of many considerations when creating the ideal learning environment for special education students. This is one of the many reasons why you should be familiar with educational psychology. Because people can only make sense of their situation through the lens of their memories, past events and predictions, time cannot be reversed or lived in advance.

In fact, Zimbardo, and Boyd (1999) stated that the individual's current behaviors as well as personal decision-making processes are significantly affected by both the past and the predicted future of the individual. According to Gjesme (1983), the activities that individuals have soon differ from person to person. The pursuit of long-term goals is likely to drive the behavior of some people, while the pursuit of immediate goals is more likely to drive the behavior of others. The degree to which a person focuses on past events or events they believe will happen in the future is related to how they orient themselves with respect to time. According to Gjesme (1983), there are distinctions to be made between a general future orientation and a future orientation based on specific conditions. The way an individual sees the future in general is irrelevant to the way he sees the future according to certain conditions . As a result, he recommends linking FTO measurements to general conditions to avoid specific values. Gjesme (1979) argues that FTO is a one-dimensional term; however, there are four elements in the Future Tense Orientation Scale: "relevance", "expectation", "occupation" and "speed". These words define "interest", "expectation", "occupation" and " speed" .

4. By Participation Levels

How much a person thinks and worries about the future is reflected in their level of involvement. An individual's outlook and expectation of the future is what the expectation factor measures. The amount of time a person spends planning the future is linked to the level of their occupation. The speed of anything is directly proportional to how fast something else will be. Because of the importance of one's perception of time in their future, goals, and motivation levels, it has a significant impact on one's ability to be influenced by behavior. There are many different meanings

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and perspectives surrounding the expressions future time orientation, future time perspective and future attitude that can be found in research. Some psychologists emphasize the differences between these categories, emphasizing that they should be differentiated (Mamolu and Güler-Edwards, 2007). This is even though the language used in the domain can be changed. In this research, the concept of future orientation refers to expectations and beliefs about future goals in the present (Husman & Lens, 1999). The ideas of motivation, attitude, and affective elements all relate to future temporal orientation discussed here. These relationships emphasize how much a person thinks about the future, the amount of optimism they have, and the views they have about their ability to change the future (Mac Giollabhui et al., 2018). There have been many studies on future orientation relationships. These studies focused on a wide variety of factors such as self-regulation (Bembenutty and Karabenick , 2004), academic achievement (Gutiérrez-Braojos , 2015), motivation (Nuttin , 1964), achievement motivation (Gjesme , 1981), socio -regulation (Agarwal et al. others, 1983; Lee et al., 2017; Trommsdorff (Breier-Williford & Bramlett , 1995).

5. Quality of Arguments in Terms of Methodological Soundness

In an ideal setting, students are taught to accept the role played by randomness in events, to evaluate the quality of arguments in terms of methodological robustness, to grasp the distinctions between correlation and causality, to recognize and comprehend the complex and multifaceted nature of events (Lawson, 1999; Lawson et al., 2015). Therefore, there is a connection between critical thinking and research conducted in the field of psychological sciences (Meltzoff & Cooper, 2018). According to findings from recent studies, students' understanding of a subject may improve in research and statistics courses, but they may not show more interest in the subject (Sizemore & Lewandowski , 2009). To be more specific , instructors have a significant impact on the development of students' research abilities, particularly the mental component of such competencies (Udompong et al., 2014). The experience and quality of instructors have a direct impact on the level of happiness students experience in university courses (Green et al., 2015). For this reason, it is especially important to determine the effect of students' satisfaction with the research courses they take on determining their views on research.

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Most students are not phenomenally successful in trying to gather the points of direction from these sources that are inevitably necessary to fully understand a topic (understanding how its content can guide their actions). From Gal'perin 's point of view, the origin of mental processes (actions and concepts) should be the methodical and step-by-step formation of mental actions and concepts (Gal'perin , 1966). This is because we clarified these conditions simultaneously in the process of creating the conditions for actions of the required quality. The ability of the educator to choose a learning technique that forms the basis of the first, second or third type of orientation of action is one of the most important aspects of teaching. The construction of knowledge as a direction of action is supported only by the second and third types of teaching methods. The use of trial-and-error method for students to determine how to guide their own behavior is the main feature of the first type of OBA .

Students can use completely various aspects of the learning situation when searching for orientation points. These may include the teacher's explanation from a "knowledgeable" person; demonstrating a model for solving specific problems; a description rather than a description of objects grouped into a concept.

"Essentials" etc. display of a set of objects for independent comparison and identification.

The student's growing OBA often includes certain features that are irrelevant to the idea at hand and not suitable for solving that category of topic. For example, if a teacher gives students nothing but the definition of "perpendicular lines" and then assigns them problems that require the recognition of perpendicular lines (recognition actions), the students will devise a method on their own:

- (a) attributes (if a definition is given, attributes must be "subtracted" from it).*
- (b) determining their presence (or absence) in each presented object; and*
- (c) a result of whether an object belongs to this class of objects, according to a logical rule.*

First, it is important that students select from the definition the relevant properties of perpendicular lines, these are as follows:

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- (a) two lines (actually, two properties - they must be true and there must be two).
- (b) both must be straight; and
- (c) the angle between them should be equal to 90 degrees. Second, students should be able to recognize each feature shown in the items brought to their attention, and third, they should be able to apply a logical rule to reach a conclusion. (upright or not, or do we need additional information?")

most teens have a tough time doing all this on their own, their OBA is likely to be incomplete and tangible. In their seminal paper, Gal'perin and Talyzina (1957) criticized the practice of using the first type of OBA and proposed an alternative teaching method. This method makes it possible to provide the learner with appropriate quality action tools and methods and to make the given knowledge a real point of guidance for future action. In addition , Gal'perin and Talyzina (1957) suggested that the first type of OBA is more effective than the second type of OBA .

6. Students ' Participation in the Research Project

Several studies have shed light on the ways in which aspirations for the future can positively affect academic performance (Miller et al., 1996; Wigfield & Eccles , 1992). Similarly, Simons et al. (2004) emphasized the relevance of future goals as an intrinsic motivation for contemporary academic learning, perseverance, and achievement . Theorists who believe in the future tense perspective suggest that students' intentions for their future , including their educational and career paths , should be influenced by their long-term desires as well as their short-term passions. Additionally, these long-term intentions have an impact on learning styles (Kauffman and Husman , 2004; Peetsma et al., 2005). Since hopelessness is defined as the absence of optimistic future expectations (O'Connor & Cassidy , 2007), it is strongly associated with a focus on the future time. Both hope and despair are expressions of a person's assessment of the likelihood of success in achieving certain goals (Melges and Bowlby , 1969).

Taking the time to plan out how you want your life to look in the years to come is one of the most important things you can do. Although the actions and goals teens do now have a significant impact

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on their lives in the years to come, adolescents tend to be less pessimistic than adults as they focus more on the future. It is thought that the main reason for the decrease in the degree of pessimism in this age group is the increase in the cognitive abilities of young people to orient themselves towards the future (Mac Giollabhui et al.2018). According to recent research, there is a direct linear connection between students' motivations , near and far goals, learning processes and future temporal orientations. However, it is essential to determine the hopelessness levels as well as the future time orientations of the students in relation to the improvement of the level of reaching the educational goals. According to the findings of another study, there is a negative moderate relationship between future orientation in terms of time and feelings of hopelessness and depression (Breier-Williford & Bramlett , 1995). On the other hand, there are a limited number of studies that discuss the hope and hopelessness levels of music teacher candidates (Ercan & Orhan, 2019). In this context, it is important to examine the pessimism levels of music teacher candidates as well as their future time orientations. In this study, the participant's gender serves as an additional independent variable. In the academic literature , there are studies investigating whether there is a difference between future tense orientation and gender, and the findings of these studies are contradictory (Gjesme's , 1979; Mamolu and Güler-Edwards 2007). In this way, the findings of the current study will add to the existing research group.

Finally, as people age, their orientation towards the future time becomes more comprehensive (Trommsdorff , 1983). In addition, young people have goals such as education, finding a job and starting a family (Güler Edwards, 2008). Considering that individuals get closer to having a job and a family as their grades get higher, it is thought that there are differences in future time orientation and class variables. In addition, there is not a single research that can be identified in the said study investigating the relationship between grade factors and future time orientation. In the light of this information, it is necessary to examine the temporal orientations of music teacher candidates for the future in terms of the institution they go to, gender, class, and degree of despair. The Self-Determination Theory The self-determination hypothesis proposes that an individual's level of autonomy, relationship, and competence are the basic psychological demands that shape motivation levels (De Bilde et al., 2011).

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According to the theory of self-determination, "autonomy" is the most basic psychological need for every individual (Chemolli & Gagné, 2014). However, research that uses "self" as one of the structural elements for theories must include the "self" definition of the individual being studied (Kaplan et al., 2002; De Bilde et al., 2011; Guayand Bureau , 2018). Self-determined motivation is the characteristic of people's behavioral operation related to choose, that is, their sense of perceptually internal control. Self-determined motivation is also known as intrinsic motivation (Howardet et al ., 2017; Ryan and Deci , 2017, 2020). Therefore, self-determined motivation indicates that the individual can choose and choose; it is not enhanced sense or external pressure that compels the individual to do so; rather, it is the individual who makes the decision to do so (Chemolli and Gagné , 2014; Guay and Bureau , 2018).

The degree of students' motivation to learn is measured in this study using the self-determination theory of Ryan and Deci (2017, 2020). This theory was proposed by Ryan and Deci and divided into three dimensions: "intrinsic motivation ", "extrinsic motivation" and "nonmotivation".

- (1) *Intrinsic motivation indicates that an individual engages in the activity on his own initiative, and that the individual can enjoy the activity itself, which belongs to a high degree of autonomy.*
- (2) *extrinsic motivation indicates that extrinsic things are an incentive to involve individuals in various activities and this motivation exists outside the learning object.*
- (3) *intrinsic and extrinsic motivation is called "transference motivation". It was published in Frontiers in Psychology on March 2, 2022.*

Future tense orientation and learning are highly interconnected with participation and intrinsic motivation . It has been shown to have a significant impact on people's thoughts, feelings, and actions (De Bilde et al., 2011) and plays a key role in helping people understand their life experiences and explain their actions (Gutiérrez-Braojos , 2015; Lindstrom Johnson). and others).

Dynamic State and Cognition

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He defined future time orientation as a coherent disposition, a malleable and variable cognitive structure, a one-way or multi-directional structure that attracts a lot of researchers (Zhang et al., 2015; Lindstrom Johnson et al., 2016; Wong et al., 2019). For example, DeVolder and Lens (1982) took the view that it is a personality trait and subdivided it into dynamic state and cognition. Daltrey and Langer (1984) suggested that future time orientation is a multidimensional construct that includes aspects such as ductility, consistency, orientation, intensity, and attitude/emotion/emotion (De Bilde et al., 2011). Peetsma (two thousand) considered future tense orientation as a concept of motivation and divided it into three subcategories: knowledge, appraisal, and behavioral intention. Subsequent research revealed that people's perspectives on time change with age, and their personalities develop over time. According to Husman and Lens (1999), an individual's future orientation is the expected view they have towards their long-term goals. As a result of the link between students' current work, work, or academic performance and their long-term goals, people are more likely to be motivated to continue their education (Lens et al, 2002; Zhang et al, 2015). When the individual has a stronger future tense orientation, they are encouraged to engage in activities, strive, and make plans that will help them achieve their future goals. This is because when an individual has a stronger future orientation, they are more likely to develop specific future goals (Husman & Lens, 1999; De Bilde). et al., 2011; Lindstrom -Johnson et al., 2016; Wong et al ., 2019). According to Miller and Brickman (2004), future tense orientation is an incentive to achieve future goals and develops individual learners' willingness to participate in autonomous learning (Gutiérrez-Braojos , 2015).

Next, Mello and Worrell (2015) summarized future tense orientation in several key aspects:

(a) First, future time orientation is cognitive because it originates in minds; second, future tense orientation is motivated because individuals' thinking about time will prompt them to make decisions and exhibit certain behaviors; third, future tense orientation is behavioral because it causes people to act in certain ways ; and finally, future tense orientation is behavioral because it causes people to act in certain ways (Peetsma , 2000; Simons et al., 2004; Wong et al., 2019).

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- (b) *Second, ductility, density, consistency, engagement, foresight, speed, perceptibility, and value are the components that make up the measurement of future time orientation. In other words, when a person sets goals for the future, the extent to which he or she can consider the length of time and detailed plans determines the degree to which he or she is concerned about the value of reflecting on the value of both.*
- (c) *Third, the degree to which people differ in their view of the future depends on the amount of learning and social experience they gain in various settings (Miller and Brickman, 2004). In the past, Brown, and Jones (2004) believed that different views of time-oriented learners would affect their degree of participation in learning and lead to different learning outcomes (Gutiérrez-Braojos, 2015; Lindstrom-Johnson et al., 2016).*

As for the relationship between future time orientation and learning engagement, in the past, Brown and Jones (2004) believed that different views of time orientation learners would affect their degree of involvement in learning and lead to different learning outcomes. Horstmannshof and Zimitat (2007) discovered that when university students have a better future tense orientation, they have a better learning attitude or behavior. This includes mastering goals, intending to spend more time reading, adopting deeper learning strategies, and asking others for help when they have difficulties. There is a positive relationship between focusing on the future and active participation in educational efforts (King, 1984; DeBilde et al., 2011). Moreover, these internal future goals can lead to more effort, autonomous learning, and persistence in learning tasks, as well as contributing to greater conceptual learning, better performance, and higher retention in learning activities that will be relevant (Gutiérrez-Braojos, 2015). Future tense orientation is a belief or disposition towards future goals that an individual has, and this can promote learning interest, motivation, and behavioral adjustment to pursue future goals (Gutiérrez-Braojos, 2015).

Benbenutty and Karabenick (2003) believed that future time orientation is a belief or tendency towards the future goals that an individual has. Miller and Brickman (2004) proposed a self-adjusting motivational model of future orientation. They believe that the motivation of future orientation is the belief system that individuals acquire during the socialization process. This belief system can set future goals and lead learners to self-adjustment. Miller and Brickman (2004) are

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the people who developed this model. Students at various levels of high school have varying degrees of diversity when it comes to their perspectives on the future. Students are more likely to understand the relevance of their course to their lives after graduation, in direct proportion to the degree to which they are motivated to study. Research conducted by Gutiérrez-Braojos (2015) has shown that the degree to which students perceive the importance of their academic work and its potential impact on their future growth affects their willingness to study.

7. Participation in Learning

learning is a crucial factor in students' overall success (Suárez et al., 2019; Afzali and Izadpanah , 2021). Students' involvement in their own education not only reflects their willingness to study, but also helps researchers understand their future behavior and how they grow as individuals (Afzali & Izadpanah, 2021). Growth and strong academic success will be produced because of the efforts, perseverance, attention, and pleasure of individuals who actively participate in the learning process (Hsieh, 2014). On the other hand, the decrease in learning time of individuals who hesitate to participate, dropping out of school, distraction, unhappiness, and anxiety are also largely associated with dropping out (Fredricks et al., 2004; Suárez et al., 2019). [Excerpts from Fredericks et al., 2004; Suárez et al., 2019] The term "learning engagement" refers to the amount of effort and time students spend in their academic pursuits and activities (Afzali and Izadpanah , 2021). For these educational activities to be meaningful, the participation of other people is required.

Learning participation has been defined by Kuh (2003, 2009) as the process of individual action, perception and thinking in the context of students' educational experiences.

8. The Relationship between Time Perception and Future Plans

The speed of anything is directly proportional to how fast something else will be. Because of the importance of one's perception of time in their future, goals, and motivation levels, it has a

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significant impact on one's ability to be influenced by behavior. There are many different meanings and perspectives surrounding the expressions future time orientation, future time perspective and future attitude that can be found in research. Some psychologists emphasize the differences between these categories, emphasizing that they should be differentiated (Mamolu and Güler-Edwards, 2007). In this research, the concept of future orientation refers to expectations and beliefs about future goals in the present (Husman & Lens, 1999). The ideas of motivation, attitude, and affective elements all relate to future temporal orientation discussed here. These relationships emphasize how much a person thinks about the future, the amount of optimism they have, and the views they have about their ability to change the future (Mac Giollabhui et al., 2018). There have been many studies on future orientation relationships. These studies focused on a wide variety of factors such as self-regulation (Bembenutty and Karabenick , 2004), academic achievement (Gutiérrez-Braojos , 2015), motivation (Nuttin , 1964), achievement motivation (Gjesme , 1981), socio -regulation (Agarwal et al. others, 1983; Lee et al., 2017; Trommsdorff (Breier-Williford & Bramlett , 1995).

The idea of future tense orientation is also used in various fields. It has emerged as an interesting topic under research and especially for educational psychology (Eren, 2012; Eren & Tezel, 2010; Husman & Lens, 1999; Kauffman & Husman , 2004; Nuttin , 1964; Peetsma et al. , 2005; Walker & Tracey , 2012) Because education is often considered one of the best investments a person can make in life, a significant portion of the subfield of educational psychology research is about their ideas, goals, and priorities students have for their own time in the future . Students should be prepared through an informed, systematic, and sequential learning process that will enable them to develop their desire and ability to shape both their own and their community's environment through the depth and competence they gain through their personal investment. This is one of the main aims of education. Therefore, gaining an awareness of the impact of future tense orientation is a vital component in the process of analyzing how students interact with educational standards and the results of their efforts.

Several studies have shed light on how aspirations for the future can positively affect academic performance (Miller et al., 1996; Wigfield & Eccles , 1992). Similarly, Simons et al. (2004)

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CURRENT SCIENCE

emphasized the relevance of future goals as an intrinsic motivation for contemporary academic learning, perseverance, and achievement . Theorists who believe in the future tense perspective suggest that students' intentions for their future , including their educational and career paths , should be influenced by their long-term desires as well as their short-term passions. Additionally, these long-term intentions have an impact on learning styles (Kauffman and Husman , 2004; Peetsma et al., 2005). Since hopelessness is defined as the absence of optimistic future expectations (O'Connor & Cassidy , 2007), it is strongly associated with a focus on the future time. Both hope and despair are expressions of a person's assessment of the likelihood of success in achieving certain goals (Melges and Bowlby , 1969).

Taking the time to plan out how you want your life to look in the years to come is one of the most important things you can do. Although the actions and goals teens do now have a significant impact on their lives in the years to come, adolescents tend to be less pessimistic than adults because they focus more on the future. It is thought that the main reason for the decrease in the degree of pessimism in this age group is the increase in the cognitive abilities of young people to orient themselves towards the future (Mac Giollabhui et al.2018)

The findings of the same study showed that individuals with low hope levels were more likely to give up after a certain amount of work, get into a stalemate because of setting overly ambitious goals, or find themselves unsuccessful. According to the findings of another study, there is a negative moderate relationship between future orientation in terms of time and feelings of hopelessness and sadness (Breier-Williford & Bramlett , 1995). On the other hand, there are a limited number of studies investigating the degree of optimism and hopelessness experienced by music teacher candidates (Ercan & Orhan,2019). In this context, it is important to examine the pessimism levels of music teacher candidates as well as their future time orientations. In this study, the participant's gender serves as an additional independent variable. In the academic literature , there are studies investigating whether there is a difference between future tense orientation and gender, and the findings of these studies are contradictory (Gjesme's , 1979; Mamolu and Güler-Edwards 2007). In this way, the findings of the current study will add to the existing research

group. Finally, as people age, their orientation towards the future time becomes more comprehensive (Trommsdorff, 1983).

9. Youth Goals

In addition, young people have goals such as schooling, finding a job and starting a family (Güler Edwards, 2008). It is believed that there are differences in future tense orientation and grade factors if people get closer to having a career and a family as their grades get higher. In addition, there is not a single research that can be identified in the said study investigating the relationship between grade factors and future time orientation. In the light of this information, it is necessary to examine the temporal orientations of music teacher candidates for the future in terms of the institution they go to, gender, class, and degree of despair. Research communities dedicated to psychology and counseling studies have existed for hundreds of years. However, educational psychology and counseling have recently emerged as separate subfields within the broader subject of psychology. According to Mitchell and McConnell 's (2012) findings, cognitive and social cognitive theories were found to be the most frequently brought up theoretical perspectives in current discussions of educational psychology. Graves et al. (2020) recently published a bibliometric study in which they expanded their analysis to a total of nine educational psychology publications; however, they concentrated on only one issue of social justice. Considering this, while the article offers a fresh perspective on a critical issue related to educational psychology, it does not offer a comprehensive analysis of the discipline. The findings of several other studies that have attempted more complete reviews of the literature on educational psychology and counseling are presented in this section. They did a detailed analysis of various article types and content themes. Price et al. (2011) these pieces were fifty percent qualitative and fifty percent narrative, but there was not a single quantitative study presented.

As our research reveals, schema theory and motivation emerged as recurring topics in every decade of the most cited publications in this chapter. Other topics discussed in research conducted in the

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1970s included the function played by random control trials in educational psychology, the appropriate method for determining inter-interpretive reliability, and the many ways in which students' enjoyment levels could be increased. Specifically, he focused on how the theory relates to the concept of inner and outer. The ability to reflect on one's past actions and understand why they succeeded or failed is central to attribution theory. There is a relationship between a student's perspective on their future motivation and the factors they feel are responsible for their success or deficiencies as learners in the classroom.

10. Conclusion

If a student believes they have failed a test because they did not put in enough effort, they are likely to be more motivated to take the test again because they think they have control over the effort variable. If it is thought that the student's failure is caused by factors beyond his control, the student's motivation will decrease significantly. This theory was developed with the aim of improving existing motivational theories that mostly focus on pleasure seeking and avoidance of unpleasant experiences . Brophy argued that to achieve this goal, good research and data collections must be created, and that eventually, general findings on teaching in a classroom should lead to specific studies that are intended to be done situations. One factor that Brophy (1979) looked at was the impact of teachers' expectations on student achievement in the classroom. In the study of Brophy and Good (1970), it was observed that the instructors and children in four different classes of the first grade interacted with each other. The behavior of both instructors and students was the focus of the observations. They observed that students' behaviors were responsible for some differences in the behavior patterns of different instructors, while other differences in teachers' behavior patterns could not be associated with students' behaviors. The findings showed that students' ability to keep certain concepts in mind was affected by the perspective presented to them . In other words, the importance of concepts was defined from the student's perspective. This showed that the ideas in and of themselves were not important, their importance was determined by one's perspective on the book . The primary criticism addressed was the idea that the field was not making enough use of randomized controlled trials. The authors argued that there is value in

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running randomized controlled trials; however, in many cases such trials are not possible. Given the meta-topic it covers for being reasonable, it is not surprising that this article is still often cited. On the other hand, it is the only article in the top twenty to address this topic. The authors citing this article consider this to be one of the main arguments to suggest exceptions to randomized control trials and how to deal with situations where randomized controlled trials are not viable (Holland, 1986). Numerous other critical issues prevalent in the understanding of learning today have been presented and developed in other influential articles from the 1970s. Tinsley and Weiss (1975) contributed to the development of more comprehensive methods to assess inter-interpretive reliability and agreement. They also conducted the first psychological research aimed at increasing human happiness, especially among college students (Fordyce , 1977). These issues reflect larger trends, in addition to the themes discussed so far.

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